

The problems of bilingualism in Psycholinguistics

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Annotation

While it's true that bilingualism brings lots of benefits with it, there are also a number of challenges of being bilingual.

The bilingual struggles we'll cover today include four issues related to parenting and introducing the language in the home, as well as four issues related to bilingual education.

Keywords: human brain, bilingual, monolingual, brain, gender, grade.

Many children in Central Asia, even our country Uzbekistan and around the world grow up exposed to two languages from an early age, and how to best support language acquisition in their children. Families may have planned to raise their children to become bilingual, but for whatever reason, they decided to postpone [the introduction of the second family language](#).

Despite the popularity of bilingualism, surprisingly little research has been conducted on the topic, particularly on the foundations of bilingual language learning in infants and toddlers. The science of bilingualism is a young field, and definitive answers to many questions are not yet available. Furthermore, other questions are impossible to answer due to vast differences across families, communities, and cultures. But with an accumulation of research studies over the last few decades, we are now equipped to partially answer some of parents' most pressing questions about early bilingualism.

This is due to social demand or some reason. Its natural occurrence is also caused by the close living of representatives of two or more peoples on the territory of one state.

A bilingual human brain has several significant advantages. Some can even be seen: gray matter is denser. In addition, when using a second language, there is an increase in the activation of some parts of the brain. We can call it sharpening the brain.

Nowadays, the cognitive advantage of bilingualism seems very clear. But at the time it surprised the experts. Until the 1960s, bilingualism was considered a barrier to child development because it consumed the energy needed to constantly switch between languages. This view was based on scientific work that was flawed in the first place. Recent studies have confirmed that knowing several languages leads to the development of human qualities such as decision-making, switching between tasks, concentration of attention.

Many representatives of Uzbek classical literature (the Middle Ages) knew both Uzbek and Persian well. For example, Alisher Navoi knew his mother tongue - Turkish very well, as well as Persian. Many works in this language were compiled by Devon ("Devony Foniy"). This poem was highly appreciated by Persian poets, especially by Jami.

Writers who create in two languages can be found even now. In particular, the famous Kyrgyz writer Chingiz Aitmatov is a free writer in Kyrgyz and Russian languages. In

general, bilingualism as a social phenomenon is an important factor influencing the enrichment and development of languages and the increase of the universal cultural level. Any interaction between languages requires bilingual people.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Russian language is widely studied and has its position and place in the life of the country. Since the majority of the country's population knows Uzbek and Russian, we can call them bilingual. Along with Russian, other foreign languages are taught.

The phenomenon of bilingualism is a complex phenomenon and is the object of research in various disciplines, such as linguistics, psychology, and methods of teaching foreign languages.

Bilingualism is a diversified phenomenon that can be studied in different aspects. Three aspects of bilingualism are most distinguished: 1) linguistic (sociolinguistic) 2) psychological 3) pedagogical. In a multi-ethnic and multilingual state, the teaching of nations, national language policy, and language construction should be the methodological basis of studying bilingualism in all aspects.

Researchers on bilingualism have repeated over the years that half of the world's population, if not more, is bilingual. Unfortunately, there are no clear data for the whole world but it is clear that bilingualism is found in all age groups, in all levels of society, and in most countries [1].

For example, a European Commission report (2006) showed that some 56% of the inhabitants of 25 European countries speak a second language well enough to have a conversation in it. They may not all lead their lives with two or more languages but the percentage gives an idea of how extensive bilingualism can be. In North America, some 35% of the population of Canada is bilingual. The percentage is smaller in the United States (around 18–20%) but this still amounts to some 55 million inhabitants. The proportion of bilinguals is much higher in other parts of the world such as Asia and Africa where it is normal to know and use several languages in one's everyday life.

Another important reason for the extent of bilingualism is education and culture. Many students pursue their studies in a region or country with a different language to their own and hence become bilingual. Other events such as intermarriage or professional opportunities – diplomacy, business, foreign journalism, language teaching, and so on – lead to the development of language contact. The phenomenon is far more frequent than one imagines at first and it is only natural, therefore, that the language sciences have given bilingual studies much more room in recent years.

Bilinguals usually acquire and use their languages for different purposes, in different domains of life, with different people [2]. Different aspects of life often require different languages.

We think of bilingual individuals as those people who are able to speak two (or more) languages, to some level of proficiency, but identifying what counts as a language is not a straightforward judgment. We take for granted that we know what languages are – where

one stops and the next one starts. That notion, too, is illusory: the delineation of individual languages is often a matter of decree.

When this empirical paradigm is used to investigate bilingual youngsters, there are two issues. Bilingualism is not a categorical variable, to start with. Any placement of kids in a group identified as either bilingual or monolingual obscures the richness of the idea that A decrease in the complexity of children's language and bilingualism skills. Age, gender, grade, or any other conventional categories do not apply to bilingualism.

Being multilingual is a spectrum, starting with almost no awareness of other languages [3]. Languages are available to enable bilingualism.

Do we classify youngsters as bilingual on this scale? At what point on this scale do we declare children to be bilingual? How do we conduct research on the impact of a variable that we struggle to define? In the ideal research design that compares performance across groups, the two groups are exactly the same except for the single independent variable we have chosen to study. If we are to interpret any performance disparities that appear between the groups, we need to have this distinct separation between them. Significant performance discrepancies that may appear, with all other factors being equal and under control, may only be attributable to the one variable that divides the otherwise equivalent samples. The path from reviewing the data to deciphering the significance of the findings is then clear-cut. [4] The second problem is in the equivalency of the groups, even if categorical placements can be achieved. Bilingual children are never exactly the same as an otherwise comparable group of monolingual children except for the number of languages they speak. In some inevitable sense, bilingual children live different lives than their friends and neighbors who may be socially, economically, and politically similar but speak only one language. [5] Bilingual children may have different home arrangements, perhaps being cared for by an extended family member who speaks another language. Bilingual children may travel more than monolinguals, making family visits to some other homeland. Bilingual children may spend more time than monolinguals in formal schooling, attending after school or weekend classes in their other language. Any of these differences that come with the bilingual experience may itself have an impact on aspects of language and cognitive development, aside from the bilingualism per se. This situation presents an immense challenge to research. Controlled investigation of the impact that bilingualism might have on children's development requires that bilingual children are compared with equivalent monolinguals on specific aspects of performance. [6] In the absence of a truly ideal control group, every effort must be made to assure that the experiences encountered by the two groups of children in the study are as comparable as possible.

Conclusion

Bilingualism research is one of the topics that is now being studied and there are still many unanswered questions in this regard. Currently, researchers are working on the mechanism of bilingualism and the difference between the minds of bilinguals and monolinguals. Recently, brain imaging studies have been conducted to determine why and

how consciousness changes as a result of bilingualism. The answers to this question are not yet known, but scientists have some ideas about where to find the answer.

We think every family is unique. The language proficiency and preference of each family member, along with their community situation, will dictate how the family uses the two languages from day to day.

Parents must regularly appraise what languages their child is hearing at home, at school, and elsewhere and be open to adjusting language use as needed.

Although the belief that each parent should speak to their bilingual children in that parent's own native language is widespread, this one-parent-one-language (OPOL) approach is neither necessary nor sufficient for successful bilingual acquisition.

Instead, families often find that the use of the two languages without fixed rules leads to balanced exposure.

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